

Assessment of Health-Related Physical Fitness in Adolescents: Prevalence of Risk Indicators in High School Students

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Abstract — Physical fitness is the ability to perform daily tasks with vigor and alertness, without excessive fatigue, and with enough energy to enjoy leisure activities and handle unexpected emergencies. When related to health, physical fitness involves components associated with physical, psychological, and social well-being, both in terms of disease prevention and risk reduction, as well as greater readiness for daily activities. **Objective:** To assess health-related physical fitness in high school students. **Methods:** Body composition was evaluated using the body mass index (BMI) and the waist-to-height ratio (WHtR), classified into the Healthy Zone (HZ) and the Health Risk Zone (HRZ), along with body fat percentage (%BF). The 2021 version of the PROESP-BR test battery was used to assess physical capacities. Flexibility (FL) was measured using the sit-and-reach test; abdominal endurance (AE) was evaluated through the one-minute sit-up test; the 20-meter sprint test was used to assess speed; and the 6-minute walk/run test was applied for cardiorespiratory endurance (CE). **Results:** Girls and boys had similar ages (16 ± 0.82 vs. 16 ± 0.9 ; $p>0.05$), weights (52.3 ± 8.08 vs. 58.6 ± 12 ; $p<0.05$), heights (1.59 ± 0.05 vs. 1.71 ± 0.06 ; $p<0.05$), and BMIs (20.8 ± 3.1 vs. 20.1 ± 3.17 ; $p>0.05$). Regarding BMI, both sexes were mostly in the HZ (79.8% vs. 87.8%; $p>0.05$). The same was observed for WHtR (96.2% vs. 97.6%; $p>0.05$). Girls showed a higher %BF than boys (26 ± 4.21 vs. 19.5 ± 7.47 ; $p<0.05$). In the %BF classification, the distribution was: adequate (46.2% vs. 52.4%), moderate (33.7% vs. 32.9%), high (20.2% vs. 8.5%), and only boys reached the excessively high category (6.1%). Girls achieved higher values than boys in the FL test (41.3 ± 9.99 vs. 35.5 ± 11.2 ; $p<0.05$). Boys performed better in AE (27 ± 8.41 vs. 33 ± 7.65 ; $p<0.05$), CE (815 ± 149 vs. 1037 ± 201 ; $p>0.05$), and speed (5.39 ± 0.93 vs. 4.2 ± 0.59 ; $p<0.05$). In the FL classification, both sexes were within the HZ, although a higher percentage of girls were in the HZ (60.6% vs. 58.5%), while boys had more individuals in the HRZ (39.4% vs. 41.5%; $p>0.05$). For AE, both groups were predominantly in the HRZ (94% vs. 92.7%), with few reaching the HZ (5.8% vs. 7.3%; $p>0.05$). A similar pattern occurred in speed performance, with nearly identical HRZ proportions between girls and boys (95.2% vs. 95.1%) and HZ (4.8% vs. 4.9%; $p>0.05$). In CE, 96.2% of the girls were in the HRZ, and although most of the boys were also in this classification (78%), a slightly higher proportion reached the HZ compared to girls (22% vs. 4.8%; $p<0.05$). **Conclusion:** Girls demonstrated greater FL capacity, while boys performed better in AE, CE, and speed. Both sexes showed a health-related physical fitness (HRPF) level predominantly classified within the HRZ for most variables, which is concerning given that such patterns are already evident during adolescence.

Keywords — Physical activity, High school, Students, Health, Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of physical fitness has evolved over the years. Recently, the American College of Sports Medicine defined physical fitness as the ability to perform daily tasks with vigor and alertness, without undue fatigue, and with sufficient energy to enjoy leisure activities and respond to unexpected emergencies [1]. Health-related physical fitness encompasses components associated with physical, psychological, and social well-being, both in terms of disease prevention and risk reduction, as well as increased readiness for daily life activities [2].

The increasing prevalence of obesity among children and adolescents poses a major public health challenge worldwide, as it is associated with poor health outcomes during childhood, adolescence, and adulthood. Obesity also negatively impacts health-related physical fitness, which is commonly defined in terms of cardiorespiratory endurance, muscular strength and endurance, flexibility, among other components [3].

Furthermore, the consequences of a sedentary lifestyle include the development of numerous risk factors for noncommunicable chronic diseases (NCDs), which can significantly limit individuals' physical fitness [4].

However, a high proportion of Brazilian adolescents do not meet the recommended levels of health-related physical fitness (HRPF). Considering that many health problems are linked to low physical fitness and that its development often begins in childhood or adolescence, this situation must be addressed. Identifying factors associated with low HRPF can provide useful insights for designing specific interventions for different groups [5].

Operationally, the components of HRPF include indicators of cardiorespiratory capacity, muscular strength/endurance, flexibility, and body composition. Assessing these indicators provides valuable information for both health-focused Physical Education programs and sports training contexts. In this regard, the evaluation of HRPF is seen as essential within the school environment [6].

Cardiorespiratory endurance and speed are closely associated with health and disease prevention, improving the performance of daily activities and potentially reducing the development of conditions such as obesity, cardiovascular diseases, and diabetes—thus promoting health and quality of life [7]. Flexibility refers to the range of motion of a joint, while muscular strength/endurance refers to the ability of a muscle or group of muscles to sustain repeated contractions over a given period [8]. According to the author, both are influenced by factors such as physical activity level, type of activity, sex, and age.

The school environment, along with childhood and adolescence, provides a suitable setting for the development of HRPF, as a physically active child is more likely to become a physically active adult, thereby reducing the likelihood of developing hypokinetic diseases. Growth rates, physical fitness, and lifestyle habits have all been linked to population health levels. Thus, individuals with more active lifestyles tend to have better HRPF, while low physical fitness levels are also associated with lifestyle changes [6].

Physical Education, therefore, becomes the most appropriate means for this purpose, as it allows children and adolescents to engage in a wide variety of motor experiences. This promotes repeated execution of individual or combined movements, fostering the development of their physical abilities and potential [9].

II. METHODS

A. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Students included in the study were those within the established age range (14 to 17 years), of both sexes, and officially enrolled in the educational institution. Exclusion criteria comprised students using medications that affect the central nervous or cardiovascular systems, those who were pregnant, had physical or mental disabilities, or did not complete the assessment tests.

B. Anthropometry

Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated using the formula: $\text{weight}/\text{height}^2$, and categorized into Healthy Zone (HZ) and Health Risk Zone (HRZ) [10]. Height (cm) was measured using a portable stadiometer with 0.1 cm precision, and weight (kg) was measured using an Omron HBF-514F scale. The waist-to-height ratio was also calculated and classified as either HZ or HRZ.

Body fat percentage (%BF) was determined using the Slaughter protocol [11], in which two skinfolds were measured (triceps and subscapular). Results were classified as: low, adequate, high, moderately high, and excessively high. An AVANUTRI skinfold caliper was used for the measurements.

C. Health-Related Physical Fitness (HRPF)

The PROESP-BR physical fitness assessment battery was used to evaluate the participants [10]. The results were categorized into Healthy Zone (HZ) and Health Risk Zone (HRZ).

Flexibility (FX) was assessed using the sit-and-reach test. A measuring tape was fixed to the floor with adhesive tape placed at the 38.1 cm mark, and a second piece of tape measuring 30 cm was positioned perpendicular to the tape. Participants sat with the zero end of the tape between their legs, heels nearly touching the tape at the 38.1 cm mark, feet approximately 30 cm apart, knees extended, and hands overlapping. Participants reached forward with their hands as far as possible. Two attempts were allowed, and the best result was recorded.

Abdominal endurance (AE) was evaluated over one minute, during which participants performed the maximum number of sit-ups. Sit-ups were performed with the participant in a supine position, knees bent at 90 degrees, arms crossed over the chest; the evaluator held the participant's feet against the floor. Upon the evaluator's signal, the participant began the test. A repetition was counted when the elbows touched the distal part of the thighs.

Speed was assessed using the 20-meter sprint test. A 22-meter course was marked, with cones placed at the starting line (0 meters), 20 meters, and 22 meters. Participants were instructed to run as fast as possible past the last cone. The evaluator positioned the participant at the starting line and recorded the time as the participant passed the 20-meter cone.

Finally, cardiorespiratory endurance (CE) was evaluated using the six-minute walk/run test. A marked circuit was established, and participants were instructed to complete as many laps as possible within six minutes. At the end of the test, the total distance covered by each student was measured.

D. Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Jamovi software version 2.3.28. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to assess data normality. Categorical variables were compared between groups using Pearson’s Chi-square test. For parametric quantitative variables (flexibility, abdominal endurance, speed, cardiorespiratory endurance, and height), the independent Student’s t-test was used, and results were presented as mean ± standard deviation. Non-parametric variables (weight, BMI, body fat percentage, and age) were compared using the Mann-Whitney U test. A significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) was adopted for all analyses.

III.RESULTS

This study evaluated a total of 186 students, including girls (n=104) and boys (n=82). According to the results (Table 1), both groups presented similar ages, girls (16±0.82 years) and boys (16±0.9 years; $p>0.05$), as well as similar BMI values (20.8±3.1 kg/m² vs. 20.1±3.17 kg/m²; $p>0.05$). For the variables weight (52.3±8.08 kg vs. 58.6±12 kg; $p<0.05$) and height (1.59±0.05 m vs. 1.71±0.06 m; $p<0.05$), boys presented higher values.

Table I. Anthropometric characterization of the sample.

	Girls	Boys	p
Age (years)	16±0.82	16±0.9	# $p>0.05$
Weight (kg)	52.3±8.08	58.6±12	# $p<0.05$
BMI (kg/m ²)	20.8±3.1	20.1±3.17	# $p>0.05$
BF (%)	26±4.21	19.5±7.47	# $p<0.05$
Height (m)	1.59±0.05	1.71±0.06	$p<0.05$

Data expressed as median ± standard deviation; BMI = Body Mass Index; %BF = Body Fat Percentage; # = non-parametric variables; kg = kilograms; kg/m² = kilograms per square meter; % = percent; m = meters.

When BMI was categorized (Figure 1), most individuals of both sexes were classified in the Healthy Zone (HZ) (79.8% vs. 87.8%), with a slightly higher proportion among males, and fewer were in the Health Risk Zone (HRZ) (20.2% vs. 12.2%; $p>0.05$).

Fig. 1. Body Mass Index classification. Data expressed as percentages. Pearson’s Chi-square test; HZ = Healthy Zone; HRZ = Health Risk Zone.

The same trend was observed for the waist-to-height ratio (Figure 2), with most participants classified in the HZ (96.2% vs. 97.6%) and very few in the HRZ (3.8% vs. 2.4%; $p>0.05$).

Fig. 2. Waist-to-height ratio classification. Data expressed as percentages. Pearson’s Chi-square test; HZ = Healthy Zone; HRZ = Health Risk Zone.

However, girls had a higher %BF compared to boys (26±4.21% vs. 19.5±7.47%; p<0.05). When comparing body fat percentage classifications, a statistically significant difference between groups was found (p<0.05) (Figure 3). Girls showed a lower proportion in the moderately high %BF category compared to boys (46.2% vs. 52.4%), while both sexes had similar proportions in the adequate category (33.7% vs. 32.9%). However, a higher percentage of girls were classified as having high %BF (20.2% vs. 8.5%), and only boys were classified in the excessively high category (6.1%).

Fig. 3. Body fat percentage classification. Data expressed as percentages. Pearson’s Chi-square test; * = statistically significant difference (p<0.05).

Regarding the components of Health-Related Physical Fitness (HRPF), girls performed better than boys in the flexibility test (41.3±9.99 cm vs. 35.5±11.2 cm; p<0.05). However, boys outperformed girls in abdominal endurance (27±8.41 reps/min vs. 33±7.65 reps/min; p<0.05), cardiorespiratory endurance (815±149 m vs. 1037±201 m; p<0.05), and speed (5.39±0.93 s vs. 4.2±0.59 s; p<0.05) (Table 2). These results indicate that females tend to be more flexible, while males tend to have greater endurance and speed.

Table II. Test results.

Variables	Girls	Boys	p
Flexibility (cm)	41.3±9.99	35.5±11.2	p<0.05
Abdominal endurance (reps/min)	27±8.41	33±7.65	p<0.05
Cardiorespiratory endurance (m)	815±149	1037±201	p<0.05
Speed (s)	5.39±0.93	4.2±0.59	p<0.05

Data expressed as mean ± standard deviation; reps/min = repetitions per minute; m = meters; s = seconds.

When results were categorized, both sexes were within the HZ for flexibility. Although girls had a slightly higher percentage in the HZ (60.6% vs. 58.5%), boys had a slightly higher proportion in the HRZ (39.4% vs. 41.5%; $p>0.05$) (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Flexibility classification. Data expressed as percentages. Pearson's Chi-square test; HZ = Healthy Zone; HRZ = Health Risk Zone.

For abdominal endurance, both groups predominantly fell within the HRZ (94% vs. 92.7%), with only a few individuals reaching the HZ classification (5.8% vs. 7.3%; $p>0.05$) (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. Abdominal endurance classification. Data expressed as percentages. Pearson's Chi-square test; HZ = Healthy Zone; HRZ = Health Risk Zone.

A similar trend was observed for the speed test, where girls and boys had nearly identical percentages of individuals in the HRZ (95.2% vs. 95.1%) and HZ (4.8% vs. 4.9%; $p>0.05$) (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Speed classification. Data expressed as percentages. Pearson’s Chi-square test; HZ = Healthy Zone; HRZ = Health Risk Zone.

For cardiorespiratory endurance (Figure 7), 96.2% of girls were classified in the HRZ, although the majority of boys were also in the same zone (78%; $p < 0.05$). Only 4.8% of girls and 22% of boys reached the HZ classification.

Fig. 7. Cardiorespiratory endurance classification. Data expressed as percentages. Pearson’s Chi-square test; HZ = Healthy Zone; HRZ = Health Risk Zone.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Anthropometry

The results of the present study are consistent with the findings of [12], as the majority of the sample was classified within the Healthy Zone (HZ) (81.94%), with only a small portion in the Health Risk Zone (HRZ) (18.05%). Studies such as [13] have observed the influence of BMI on abdominal endurance and concluded that higher BMI levels tend to negatively affect performance. However, most participants in this study presented BMI levels considered to be within the healthy range.

Regarding the waist-to-height ratio (WHtR), most groups showed values within the HZ, corroborating the findings of [14], whose study reported that 84.6% of the sample was within the HZ. Similarly, reference [15] found that both sexes largely achieved an appropriate WHtR (girls = 77.8%; boys = 81.6%). The author suggests that WHtR is a valuable complement to BMI, as it accounts for central fat distribution in relation to height, making it a critical measurement during adolescence. In a study by [16] analyzing male and female students from public and private schools, only boys from private schools presented a WHtR above the recommended level.

Regarding body fat percentage (%BF), girls showed higher %BF values than boys, in agreement with [17], which reported girls = 32.7% and boys = 20.8%. For the variables of weight (52.3 ± 8.08 vs. 58.6 ± 12), the previously cited authors also compared groups with higher and lower cardiovascular risk and found that those with lower risk had lower %BF, in both sexes.

Study [18] analyzed individuals (girls and boys) aged 13 to 16 years in three different cities. When comparing %BF, the authors found that in all cities, girls had a higher %BF than boys. In this context, [19] points out that differences in body composition between sexes are due to the fact that boys tend to develop more muscle mass due to increased levels of circulating

testosterone, whereas girls experience a predominant gain in adipose tissue due to lower testosterone levels and higher estradiol levels.

B. Components of Health-Related Physical Fitness (HRPF)

The flexibility (FX) values observed align with those reported in [20], where girls achieved an average of 41.56 ± 9.6 cm and boys 36.16 ± 10 cm. Similar findings appear in studies like [21] (girls = 31.5 cm; boys = 30 cm) and [22] (girls = 34.58 ± 9.3 ; boys = 29.85 ± 9.8).

In the FX classification (Figure 4), both sexes were predominantly categorized in the HZ. These results support those of [23], who found that the majority of both sexes were in the healthy zone: girls (90%) and boys (70%). Reference [24], analyzing individuals aged 12 to 17 years, also observed a predominance in the HZ. Similarly, in [25], 76.8% of the boys and 95.9% of the girls were classified within the HZ. Thus, it is evident that females tend to perform better in flexibility than males.

To explain this difference, [26] describe that flexibility tends to increase in females during puberty, while in males, the opposite effect occurs. Reference [27] suggests that the lack of improvement in flexibility among males may be associated with longitudinal growth (growth spurts) during puberty, where bone growth outpaces the development of muscles and tendons, thereby negatively affecting this physical ability.

Males demonstrated higher values in abdominal endurance (AE), consistent with findings from [26] (girls = 27.22 ± 9.45 reps/min vs. boys = 33.7 ± 12.04 reps/min) and [28] (girls = 24.50 ± 3.10 reps/min vs. boys = 29.86 ± 4.91 reps/min).

However, in the AE classifications (Figure 5), both groups were predominantly categorized in the HRZ, as in [29], where individuals of both sexes ($n=98$), with a mean age of 16.13 ± 0.82 years, showed 77.6% of the sample in the HRZ, with girls comprising the majority (52%). In reference [30], the authors analyzed 208 adolescents (mean age = 16.49 ± 0.99), finding that 48.4% of the total sample were in the HRZ and 51.6% in the HZ. Similarly, in [31], which assessed the HRPF of first-year high school students (age = 15 ± 0.67 years), 72.7% of boys and 66.7% of girls were found in the HRZ.

Boys also showed higher values in cardiorespiratory endurance (CR). In [32], which conducted CR tests, low levels of endurance were evident, with girls covering an average of 757.2 meters and boys 976.8 meters. Similarly, [33] reported girls = 609.2 meters and boys = 869.2 meters.

In terms of classification, both sexes were largely in the HRZ, with a greater proportion among females. This trend is also observed in [34], which evaluated the physical fitness of schoolchildren aged 12 to 15 years. In all age groups, boys had higher performance, and only students aged 13 (both sexes) and 15 (boys only) reached the HZ. The author emphasizes the need to encourage children and adolescents to engage in physical activity more frequently and for longer durations. Regular physical exercise is essential for maintaining physical fitness, as physically active adolescents tend to have better cardiorespiratory fitness, flexibility, and muscular strength/endurance [35]. Conversely, a sedentary lifestyle has been increasingly associated with diagnoses of conditions such as high cholesterol, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and obesity in children and adolescents [36].

Regarding speed, boys completed the test in a shorter amount of time, consistent with [37], where girls averaged 4.50 ± 0.65 s and boys 3.74 ± 0.50 s.

In reference [38], which analyzed 1,180 individuals aged 7 to 17 years, it was observed that boys exhibited continuous improvement in speed from ages 7 to 17, whereas girls tended to plateau around age 14. The author also notes that mechanical and functional factors during sexual maturation, combined with motivation during the test, influence performance.

More recent studies, such as [33], report similar findings. Study [39] highlights the presence of research showing that speed is associated with sex, with boys achieving better results as they age. The study also emphasizes that growth and maturation influence motor abilities. Costa further argues that more studies focusing on specific abilities such as speed are needed in the literature. However, in the classification (Table 7), no significant differences were observed between sexes: HRZ = (girls = 95.2%) vs. (boys = 95.1%), and HZ = (girls = 4.8%) vs. (boys = 4.9%), consistent with findings from [40], which reported poor classification outcomes in the speed test.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that, regarding BMI, the majority of participants were classified within the Healthy Zone (HZ). These findings are relevant, as a poor BMI classification could negatively impact physical performance in fitness tests. It was also observed that both sexes predominantly exhibited a moderately high body fat percentage (%BF).

Regarding Health-Related Physical Fitness (HRPF), females demonstrated greater flexibility (FX), while males showed higher performance in abdominal endurance (AE), cardiorespiratory endurance (CR), and speed.

Overall, both sexes were largely classified within the Health Risk Zone (HRZ) for most HRPF variables, which is a concerning scenario considering that these results were observed during adolescence. One possible contributing factor to this outcome is physical inactivity or insufficient engagement in physical activity, especially given that the sample did not present alarming anthropometric values.

Future studies should consider including measures of the frequency and duration of physical activity in order to better understand this relationship.

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